

8T – Quantum Entanglement

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main features of the 8T it is possible to reason the phenomena of Quantum entanglement in a simple and elegant fashion. That is by the primordial coupling constants series which proved Bosons as net curvature of prime discrete amount. Using the prime number feature alongside with the main equation on two photons which were once close, it is possible to show that there is a constant tie or a connection between them, given by the particle wave duality.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Suppose we had two photons which are propagated in the same moment in time and each photon is moving in the opposite direction of the other:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

For simplicity for the first time we can use subscript on the photons, we can use another notation to specify the direction of propagation in the following way.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \vec{\gamma}_1 + \vec{\gamma}_2 \quad (1.44.A)$$

Because the photons are net curvature of distinct amount, which propagate in all directions, and once liberated from the lepton are independent due to their prime number feature given by the primorial function, these curvature spikes are non-vanishing and have long lifetime. Due to the particle wave duality these can be considered particles as well, and from here we can reason the phenomena of quantum entanglement. If we consider those two entities as particles which is valid perspective according to the primorial, notice that the photon without the invariant three is described by spin one-half:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

Then we have two seemingly disconnected photons in space which move in opposite direction which instantly effect each other and thus be considered as entanglement, or ghostly action at a distance. However, if we take into account the fact that the photons are net curvature diverging to all directions, even directions that the net curvature wave backward in time than these photons, no matter how far away in space are always connected. That is because there is always an intersection of the waves, so once we measure one of those two, the other is immediately modified. We have introduced the curvature code for Fermions and Bosons accordingly:

$$[\delta\ell\delta s\delta M]\delta g = 0$$

$$[\delta\ell\delta s\delta M]\delta g > 0$$

Which is to indicate that fermions are finite in size while Bosons vary in size overtime, that is due to the last term which in this case is used as an auxiliary condition given by equations (1.48) and (1.49) for Fermions and Bosons accordingly: put another way it is impossible to separate two photons in net curvature representation. The idea of two photons separated is an illusion of the particle picture. We can present it in a different angle, those two waves which propagate to opposite directions will always have a connection, if started at a joint point those waves will propagate outward to that point and by doing so cancel each other, as we did with interference.

If we define ripple operators $\check{\delta}$ from a starting area to another area, the mutual area of both will be the amount of interference.

$$\check{\delta}: A \rightarrow B$$

$$\check{\delta}: A' \rightarrow B$$

Interference will accrue at the manifold segment that is mutual to both starting point as previously mentioned.

$$\approx: A \cap A' \tag{1.61}$$

In the context of Quantum entanglement we can modify the first two equations to present the idea of propagating to opposite directions on the matrix tensor M:

$$\check{\delta}: \overleftarrow{\gamma}_1 \rightarrow M_1$$

$$\check{\delta}: \overrightarrow{\gamma}_2' \rightarrow M_2$$

$$M_1 \neq M_2$$

$$\approx: \overleftarrow{\gamma}_1 \cap \check{\delta}: \overrightarrow{\gamma}_2$$

Quantum entanglement is the result of waves intersecting and moving to all directions, including the directions which are the opposite to the trajectory of the particle in particle spin representation, those trajectories however are canceled due to another waves, this cancelation implies that the photons are always connected by some area of intersection. When we measure the first photon, we immediately measure the second as well, as they are connected by:

$$M_2 M_1 \neq 0;$$

$$0 < t < \infty$$

Some of those ideas were mentioned before, as an example the motion of a photon in all directions including those opposite in time is mentioned by Feynman in path integrations formulation of QED. The wave features of photon is well known among all, but the key reasoning of the primordial is the following: photons are net curvature that are independent, their size increase and propagate to all directions; two photons which start at a joint point cannot be separated due to those features, the intersection means it is impossible to measure a single photon in the first place.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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